

Sample Name: ctDNA-dNMPs 75x Dilution

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=====
Acq. Operator   : SYSTEM                      Seq. Line :    2
Sample Operator : SYSTEM
Acq. Instrument : HPLC-UV-FC                 Location  :    2
Injection Date  : 12/9/2020 12:49:37 PM      Inj       :    1
                                           Inj Volume: 50.000 µl
Method         : C:\Users\Public\Documents\ChemStation\3\Data\dNMP to dNTP yield 2020-12-09
                12-22-28\dNTP QUANTIFICATION.M (Sequence Method)
Last changed   : 12/9/2020 12:22:08 PM by SYSTEM
=====
    
```


Fraction Information

No Fractions found.

Area Percent Report

```

Sorted By      :      Signal
Multiplier     :      1.0000
Dilution       :      1.0000
Do not use Multiplier & Dilution Factor with ISTDs
    
```

Signal 1: VWD1 A, Wavelength=254 nm

Peak #	RetTime [min]	Type	Width [min]	Area [mAU*s]	Height [mAU]	Area %
1	1.884	BV	0.0646	11.13425	2.59732	0.8579
2	2.117	VB	0.1359	83.03999	8.18394	6.3983
3	3.713	BV R	0.0858	161.72972	28.20029	12.4615
4	4.813	BV	0.0980	359.32025	56.11141	27.6861
5	5.179	VB	0.1045	229.76360	33.61435	17.7036
6	7.712	BV R	0.1161	452.84958	60.74146	34.8926

